

Research article

Connecting Southern Khams in geolinguistics: A brief survey on ‘fish’ and ‘pig’ beyond provinces

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Abstract: This article introduces the geolinguistic methodology for the principal part of the ‘Southern Khams dialects’ in traditional Tibetan linguistics to examine the dialectal variations within them. The target dialects are spoken in the crossing area of Yunnan, Sichuan, and Tibet Autonomous Region, China, connected by two national routes—G318 and G214. The article discusses dialectal variations of two word forms—‘fish’ (*nya*) and ‘pig’ (*phag*)—in Tibetic languages, focusing on phonological features corresponding to three Literary Tibetan (LT) patterns: initial consonant corresponding to LT *ny*, vowel corresponding to LT *a* in an open syllable, and rhyme corresponding to LT *ag*.*

Keywords: Southern Khams region; Southern Route group; sDerong-nJol group; lexical form; dialectology

1. Introduction

Previous geolinguistic research on Khams Tibetan has faced the issue that linguistic data from Tibet Autonomous Region (TAR) are rarely accessible. Hence, the quantity of datasets is unbalanced between TAR and non-TAR regions. This article primarily connects the data of Khams Tibetan dialects spoken in Sichuan and Yunnan with TAR along two main traffic routes—G318 and G214—to overview a geolinguistic situation of ‘Southern Khams’. This includes dialects located in Yunnan and Sichuan as well as Chamdo Municipality and rDzayul County (Nyingkhri Municipality) beyond the Jinshajiang River.

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The target area includes the following regions:

Yunnan Province

nJol [Deqin]

mBalung [Weixi] (Budy [Badi] Township only)

Sems-kyi Nyila (rGyalthang) [Xianggelila] (except for the southern half area)

Gongshan

Sichuan Province

mBathang [Batang]

sDerong [Deirong]

Chaphreng [Xiangcheng]

Lithang [Litang] (the southwestern part only)

TAR¹

sMarkhams [Mangkang]

mDzogong [Zuogong]

rDzayul [Chayu] (Tshawarong [Chawalong] Township)

The article principally deals with Khams Tibetan,² although other languages are also spoken in the target area, such as Lisu (Mu and Sun 2012, Suzuki 2019a), Naxi (He 2015), Nosu, Selibu (Zhou 2018, Zhou and Suzuki 2020, 2022), Nung, Trung (Qin and Suzuki 2016), Lamo, Larong sMar, and Drag-yab sMar (Suzuki et al. 2018, 2021ac, 2022ab; Tashi Nyima and Suzuki 2019), as well as various regiolects of Southwestern Mandarin. See Roche and Suzuki (2017) for their distribution (except for TAR).

Map 1 shows the target area and location of the varieties by province. Generally, geolinguistic studies do not limit specific administrative units; rather, they consider linguistic and cultural areas. Among the previous studies in the present target area, we find, for example, Suzuki (2018, 2021) for Yunnan Tibetan. However, linguistic classification, as in Map 2, is different from the boundary of administrative units. The target varieties belong to various dialectal groups, including Southern Route (SR), sPomgorgang (PG), Chaphreng (CP), sDerong-nJol (DJ), rDzayul (DZ), and Sems-kyi-nyila (SN) from Khams Tibetan, as well as Amdo Tibetan (AM).³

¹ See, for example, Suzuki et al. (2021b) for a geolinguistic approach to Tibetic varieties in the TAR's target region.

² A similar approach is taken by Suzuki (2022b) on the word form for 'dog'.

³ Based on the description of Suzuki (2018abc) with updates of Suzuki (2020, 2022). The classification of SR is preliminary and warrants a rigorous examination. See also Tournadre and Suzuki (2022).

Fig. 1 Target area and data points for mapping.

Fig. 2 Language classification in the target area.

This article examines sounds of two monosyllabic words—‘fish’ and ‘pig’. Their Literary Tibetan (LT) forms are *nya* and *phag*, respectively. It focuses on three of their features:

- (1) Head of ‘fish’: initial consonant corresponding to LT *ny*;
- (2) Tail of ‘fish’: vowel corresponding to LT *a* in an open syllable; and
- (3) Tail of ‘pig’: rhyme corresponding to LT *ag*.

We do not discuss the initial consonant of the word form for ‘pig’, as it is characterised as /p^h/; however, in Amdo Tibetan and a few other varieties, it corresponds to /h/. See also Suzuki (2007, 2019b). For the phonetic description in the data, we follow Suzuki’s (2016) method.

2. Head of ‘fish’

This section examines the initial consonant corresponding to LT *ny*. As Map 3 displays, two sound correspondences are attested in the target area.

Fig. 3 Initial consonant of the word form for ‘fish’.

Type /ŋ/ is ubiquitous, and Type /n/ is marked in the Tibetic languages. As Map 3 shows, the latter appears principally in sMarkhams as well as mDzogong counties. The distribution range is characterised by Route G318 between the Jinshajiang and Nujiang rivers. Notably, along the Jinshajiang River, some varieties use Type /ŋ/, while some others use Type /n/. The river has probably been a boundary of the given linguistic feature; however, we must investigate the mutual relationship, including intermarriage and business traffic, between the riversides.

This classification influences the word forms for ‘fish’ in non-Tibetic languages. For example, the Lamei dialect of Lamo uses /nɛ/ ‘fish’, which can be borrowed from the donor language (Tibetic) using Type /n/. Map 3 shows that Tibetic varieties used in the Lamo-speaking area belong to Type /n/. Therefore, it is reasonable that Lamo has borrowed the word from a variety distributed in its vicinity.

3. Tail of ‘fish’

This section examines the vowel corresponding to LT *a* in an open syllable. As Map 4 displays, six sound correspondences are attested in the target area.

The unmarked sound is /a/, which is assumed to be a straightforward sound correspondence with LT *a*. Type /a/ is the most widely distributed. Of the remaining sounds, /e/ is considered exceptional as a sound corresponding to LT *a* in Tibetic languages. A similar sound is known as ‘brightening’ (Matisoff 2004) in languages of the Qiangic and rGyalrongic branches, including Lamo, Larong sMar, and Drag-yab sMar; see some lexical forms cited in Suzuki et al. (2018, 2021ab, 2022a) and Tashi Nyima and Suzuki (2019).

We analyse the other sounds as follows: The sound /ɐ/ is considerably close to the unmarked type /a/, which is only attested in the Myigzur dialect. The remaining three sounds /ɑ, ɔ, o/ form a category that can be labelled as the ‘back’ vowel. We can hypothesise a sound change process /ɑ/ > /ɔ/ > /o/ based on the synchronic distribution. Note that the sound /o/ is found more widely in the east of the target area (dialects of the sPomborgang group); see Suzuki (2018ac), Li and Suzuki (2020), and Suzuki and Li (2022).

Fig. 4 Vowel of the word form for 'fish'.

4. Tail of 'pig'

This section examines the rhyme corresponding to LT *ag* in an open syllable. As the sound correspondence of LT *ag* is concerned, a glide is also included despite its phonological status as part of initial consonant clusters. As Map 5 displays, eight sound correspondences are attested in the target area.

Fig. 5 Rhyme of the word form for 'pig'.

The unmarked sound is /aʔ/; it is the most widely distributed. A similar form /aʔ/ is found around Type /aʔ/. Type /ɔaʔ/ is only found in the mBathang dialect; owing to its phonetic feature, we believe that it is derived from the back vowel form /aʔ/. Type /aq/ is found only in Amdo Tibetan. The remaining form is connected to front mid vowels /e/ and /ɛ/, as well as a palatal glide /j/, which we call Type E for simplicity. These types are principally found in varieties along the Jinshajiang River. From the geolinguistic viewpoint, the form of the mBathang dialect (Type /ɔaʔ/) is peculiar, as it is surrounded by varieties using Type E. Type E was once discussed in varieties distributed in a wider region (Suzuki 2007:37-38), displaying a scattered distribution

(see also Suzuki 2010, 2011). Map 5 shows that the distribution of Type E expands to a certain geographical range; hence, we can collect more data to examine whether these varieties can form an independent dialect (sub-)group.

5. Conclusion

The article examined three linguistic phenomena to overview the geolinguistic situation of ‘Southern Khams’, including dialects located in Yunnan and Sichuan as well as TAR. They are (1) initial consonant corresponding to LT *ny*, (2) vowel corresponding to LT *a* in an open syllable, and (3) rhyme corresponding to LT *ag*. Each linguistic map shows different distribution patterns of the given features in the target area. The results suggest a possibility of further division into (sub-)groups of Khams Tibetan, including varieties spoken in TAR.

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